

TRANSFORMING MUNICIPAL WASTE MANAGEMENT: A CASE STUDY OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY PROJECT IN SIERRA DE CÁDIZ

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ABSTRACT

The Sierra de Cádiz Circular Economy Project (ECSCA) represents a groundbreaking effort in the Sierra de Cádiz region of Andalusia, Spain, to reform municipal waste management by transitioning to a circular economy. This initiative, led by the Andalusian Government and the Sierra de Cádiz Municipalities Association, confronts the environmental and economic deficiencies of traditional linear systems. ECSCA's multi-faceted strategy encompasses a door-to-door (PaP) collection system, decentralized composting, and localized waste treatment facilities, aiming to enhance resource recovery and minimize waste generation.

With the implementation of the PaP system, significant improvements have been observed in selective waste collection rates and the purity of collected materials, demonstrating the system's efficacy in encouraging proper waste segregation. Decentralized composting, through various scales of operation, has effectively redirected organic waste from landfills, generating high-quality compost for local use.

ECSCA has spurred socio-economic growth by creating green jobs and catalyzing regional economic development, emphasizing the importance of locally tailored waste management solutions. Environmental gains include a reduction in landfill waste, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and increased resource recovery, with the added benefit of a reduced environmental footprint due to minimized waste transportation.

Despite challenges such as altering residents' habits and customizing the PaP system, ECSCA has made strides through targeted awareness campaigns and community engagement. The project's capacity for replication offers valuable insights into the importance of engaging citizens, adapting waste management practices to community needs, and adopting a phased implementation strategy.

Looking ahead, ECSCA plans to extend its reach across the region, enhance collection and composting rates, and incorporate additional waste streams. As a leading example of waste management within a circular economy framework, ECSCA aims to cement its status as a transformative model, contributing to a sustainable and resilient future.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Composting, Landfill, Recycling, Waste.

Cite this Article: Germán Coca López, Transforming Municipal Waste Management: A Case Study of The Circular Economy Project in Sierra De Cádiz, International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering Research and Development (IJEEERD), 2(2), 2024, pp. 1-14.

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJEEERD?Volume=2&Issue=2>

1. INTRODUCTION: THE URGENT NEED FOR CIRCULAR ECONOMY MODELS IN MUNICIPAL WASTE MANAGEMENT

The global shift towards a circular economy represents a paradigm shift in how we approach production, consumption, and waste management. This transition is driven by the urgent need to address the environmental challenges posed by the traditional linear economic model, characterized by its "take-make-dispose" approach, which results in resource depletion, pollution, and climate change. Municipal waste management stands as a critical area where the principles of the circular economy can be applied to achieve significant environmental and socio-economic benefits.

Traditional waste management models, often reliant on landfills and incineration, have proven inadequate in achieving high recycling rates and effectively managing the growing volume of waste generated globally.

The circular economy has gained significant attention in recent years as a sustainable alternative to the traditional linear economy model. Studies have shown that the circular economy can reduce waste, promote resource efficiency, and create new economic opportunities [1][2]. However, the implementation of circular economy models in municipal waste management remains a challenge, requiring significant changes in infrastructure, policies, and behaviors [3].

This paper examines the Circular Economy Project in Sierra de Cádiz (ECSCA), a pioneering initiative in southern Spain aimed at revolutionizing municipal waste management through the implementation of a comprehensive circular economy model. The ECSCA highlights the practical application of circular economy principles in a real-world setting, demonstrating the potential for achieving significant environmental and socio-economic improvements through innovative waste management practices.

This paper aims to:

- Analyse the implementation of the ECSCA, examining its key features, including the door-to-door (PaP) collection system and decentralized composting approaches.
- Evaluate the project's impacts, assessing its effectiveness in increasing recycling rates, diverting organic waste from landfills, creating green jobs, and fostering a new environmental consciousness among citizens.
- Discuss the replicability of the ECSCA model, exploring its potential for adaptation and implementation in other regions seeking to transition towards a circular economy in municipal waste management.

By examining the ECSCA's successes, challenges, and lessons learned, this paper seeks to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on circular economy practices in waste management and provide insights for policymakers, practitioners, and communities striving to create a more sustainable future.

While previous studies have explored the implementation of circular economy principles in municipal waste management, such as the cases of Brazil [4], Indonesia [5], and Amsterdam [6], this paper presents a unique contribution to the existing literature by focusing on the Sierra de Cádiz region in Spain. Unlike previous studies, which have primarily focused on urban areas, this paper examines the implementation of a circular economy model in a rural region, highlighting the challenges and opportunities associated with this context. Furthermore, this paper provides a more in-depth analysis of the social and economic impacts of the circular economy model, including the creation of green jobs and the stimulation of local economic development. Additionally, this paper presents a more comprehensive evaluation of the circular economy model, including an assessment of its environmental impacts and the identification of areas for improvement. Overall, this paper provides a distinct perspective on the implementation of circular economy principles in municipal waste management, highlighting the importance of considering the specific context and needs of each region.

2. BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

2.1. The Challenge of Municipal Waste Management

Traditional waste management models, characterized by a linear approach of collecting, transporting, and disposing of waste in landfills or incinerators. These models, relying heavily on landfills and incineration, have proven inadequate in effectively managing municipal waste and achieving the recycling rates necessary for a sustainable future, have several limitations:

Low Recycling Rates: These models struggle to achieve high recycling rates. In Andalusia, only 13.13% of the 4 579 800 tonnes of municipal waste generated in 2020 was collected separately for recycling [7]. This is significantly lower than the national average for Spain, where 22.68% of the 22 411 000 tonnes of municipal waste generated was segregated for recycling [7]. These low recycling rates represent a missed opportunity for resource recovery and contribute to the depletion of natural resources.

Landfill Dependence: Heavy reliance on landfills poses environmental risks, including soil and water contamination, greenhouse gas emissions, and the loss of valuable land. Landfills are also finite resources, and their capacity is increasingly strained by the growing volume of waste generated globally.

Several key challenges associated with these models can be highlighted:

Inefficiency in Resource Recovery: The sources emphasize that traditional waste management systems have consistently failed to achieve high rates of resource recovery and recycling. For over thirty years, these models, based on containerized collection and centralized treatment plants, have resulted in dismal recovery and recycling rates. In many regions of Andalusia, these rates barely surpass 6% [7], falling far short of the targets set by current regulations. This failure to efficiently capture and recycle valuable materials represents a significant loss of resources and perpetuates a linear, wasteful approach to consumption.

Environmental Impacts of Landfills: The sources highlight the environmental consequences associated with heavy reliance on landfills. Landfills pose a threat to soil and water quality due to the potential for leachate contamination. Additionally, they are significant contributors to greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane, a potent greenhouse gas that contributes to climate change. The continued expansion of landfills also leads to the loss of valuable land that could be used for other purposes.

Financial and Social Costs: Traditional waste management models are financially burdensome, requiring significant investments in infrastructure, transportation, and landfill management. The sources point to the need for a more cost-effective approach that minimizes transportation distances and promotes local resource recovery. Moreover, traditional waste management systems often lack community engagement and fail to empower citizens to actively participate in waste reduction and recycling efforts.

The sources underscore the urgent need to transition away from these inefficient and environmentally damaging models towards a more circular approach to municipal waste management that prioritizes resource recovery, waste minimization, and citizen engagement.

2.2. The Circular Economy Imperative

The circular economy offers a transformative alternative to the linear model. Its principles include:

- **Designing out waste and pollution:** Products and processes are designed to minimize waste generation and prevent pollution throughout their life cycle.
- **Keeping products and materials in use:** Products are designed for durability, repair, and reuse, extending their lifespan and reducing the need for new materials.
- **Regenerating natural systems:** Biological resources are managed sustainably to ensure their regeneration and prevent ecosystem degradation.

By embracing these principles, the circular economy has the potential to:

- **Address environmental challenges:** The transition towards a circular economy can help mitigate climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with waste management and resource extraction. It can also contribute to cleaner air and water, and healthier ecosystems.
- **Promote sustainable development:** The circular economy can foster economic growth by creating new markets for recycled materials and products. It can also create green jobs and enhance social well-being by promoting equitable access to resources and reducing environmental inequalities.

2.3. Policy and Regulatory Framework

A supportive policy and regulatory framework is crucial for driving the transition to a circular economy. Several key initiatives at the European, Spanish, and Andalusian levels have laid the groundwork for promoting circularity in waste management:

- **European Commission's Circular Economy Action Plans:** The European Commission adopted Action Plans in 2015 and 2020, outlining strategies to accelerate Europe's transition towards a circular economy. These plans encompass a wide range of measures, including promoting eco-design, fostering sustainable consumption, and reducing waste generation.
- **Spain's Circular Economy Strategy (EEEC):** Aligned with the European Commission's plans, the EEEC establishes specific targets for 2030, focusing on areas such as waste reduction, recycling, and the creation of a market for secondary raw materials.
- **Andalusia's Integrated Waste Management Plan (PIRec 2030):** This plan provides a strategic framework for waste prevention and management in Andalusia, with a strong emphasis on promoting a circular economy. It aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from waste by encouraging separate collection and reducing organic waste disposal in landfills.

These policy initiatives, along with supportive legislation like the European Union's Waste Directives and Spain's Law 7/2022 on Waste, provide a robust framework for advancing circular economy practices in waste management.

2.4. The Sierra de Cádiz Context

Sierra de Cádiz, a region in southern Spain, presents unique characteristics that made it an ideal location for piloting the ECSCA:

- **Rural Nature:** The region's rural setting, with a population of 115 000 spread across 19 municipalities ranging in size from 500 to 30 000 inhabitants, allows for the implementation of door-to-door (PaP) collection systems and localized composting initiatives, which may be more challenging to implement in densely populated urban areas.
- **Diverse Urban Development:** The region encompasses a mix of small villages, dispersed settlements, and areas with more concentrated urban development. This diversity provided an opportunity to test and adapt the ECSCA model to different settlement patterns, including the use of communal collection points and restricted-access containers in areas where traditional door-to-door collection was not feasible.
- **Need for Economic and Social Revitalization:** Sierra de Cádiz has faced challenges with high unemployment rates and social marginalization. The ECSCA offered a potential solution by creating green jobs in waste collection, education, and composting, contributing to local economic development and social well-being.

These factors made Sierra de Cádiz a suitable testing ground for the ECSCA, demonstrating the model's adaptability to diverse contexts and its potential for addressing pressing socio-economic and environmental challenges.

3. THE ECSCA: IMPLEMENTATION AND KEY FEATURES

3.1. Project Objectives

The ECSCA has a quadruple vocation and aims to create a new model of environmental awareness, impacting consumption habits and, indirectly, production models by involving citizens. Its objectives encompass social, economic, environmental, and replicability aspects:

- **Social:** The project aims to:
 - Promote green employment in an area with high unemployment rates, particularly targeting individuals at risk of vulnerability.
 - Reduce the poverty rate.
 - Empower citizens to become protagonists in environmental improvement efforts.
- **Economic:** The project seeks to:
 - Develop a robust business network within the region, fostering economic growth.
 - Utilize and apply information and communication technologies to facilitate project development.
 - Expand the network of facilities dedicated to resource recovery from waste, ensuring a fair distribution of generated wealth and decentralized waste management.
- **Environmental:** The project is committed to:
 - Raising environmental awareness among citizens.
 - Meeting reduction, recovery, preparation for reuse, and recycling targets set by European, national, and regional plans and regulations.
 - Significantly reducing the carbon footprint associated with waste management.
- **Replicability:** The ECSCA is designed as a demonstrative model intended to be replicable and adaptable to other regions of Andalusia, serving as a reference for transitioning towards a circular economy in municipal waste management.

3.2. Geographic and Material Scope

Geographic Scope: The ECSCA is being implemented in the Mancomunidad de Municipios de la Sierra de Cádiz, a region covering 2 000 km² with a population of around 115 000 distributed across 19 municipalities .

Material Scope: The project addresses the management of all municipal waste fractions, with particular emphasis on:

- Organic waste
- Packaging (light packaging)
- Paper and cardboard
- Glass
- WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment)
- Construction and demolition waste (RCD)

The project also manages minor fractions like hazardous household waste, toys, and small WEEE through dedicated collection channels.

3.3. The Door-to-Door (PaP) Collection System

The PaP system forms the cornerstone of the ECSCA's waste collection strategy. It involves:

- **Separate Collection:** Citizens segregate their waste into different fractions (organic, light packaging, paper-cardboard, and residual waste) and place them in designated containers outside their homes on specific days of the week. Glass collection continues to utilize a containerized system.
- **Loss of Anonymity:** Unlike traditional container-based systems, PaP eliminates the anonymity of waste disposal, fostering a sense of individual responsibility and encouraging better waste separation practices.

Advantages:

- **Improved Waste Segregation:** The PaP system significantly enhances waste segregation at the source, leading to higher quality recyclable materials and reducing contamination¹.
- **Increased Citizen Engagement:** By actively involving citizens in the waste separation process, PaP promotes a sense of responsibility and ownership, fostering a new environmental consciousness.

Specific Arrangements:

- **Densely Populated Areas:** In areas with vertical urban development (apartment blocks), the project employs two alternative approaches:
- **Restricted-Access Containers:** Containers with mechanical locks are provided, restricting access to residents of specific blocks, thereby maintaining a level of accountability.
- **Communal PaP:** Each block is equipped with multiple containers for different waste fractions, accessible only to residents, facilitating separate collection within the block.
- **Scattered Settlements:** In dispersed settlements where PaP is not economically viable, enclosed areas equipped with containers for all waste fractions are provided for residents, ensuring access to separate collection points.

3.4. Decentralized Composting

The ECSCA implements a decentralized composting system, prioritizing short management cycles and promoting resource recovery at the local level. This approach includes various composting methods:

- **Home Composting:** The project facilitated a large-scale home composting campaign, providing around 1 600 households and establishments (mostly hotels and restaurants) with the necessary materials and guidance to compost organic waste on their own, allowing them to utilize the compost produced in their homes and gardens.
- **Community Composting:** In areas where individual home composting is not feasible, the project established community composting units with large-capacity composters, enabling residents to deposit their separated organic waste and collect the resulting compost for domestic use.
- **Semi-automatic composting:** For smaller and more isolated municipalities, the project installed five semi-automatic composting units strategically located to minimize transportation distances and process organic waste collected through the PaP system efficiently.
- **Composting plant:** To manage the organic waste from the most populated municipalities, the project is constructing a shared composting facility in Villamartín, ensuring that all organic waste generated in the Sierra de Cádiz is composted within the region.

This multi-faceted approach aims to maximize organic waste diversion from landfills and create a closed-loop system for nutrient recycling within the region.

3.5. Management of Other Waste Fractions

The ECSCA utilizes distinct strategies for managing various waste fractions:

- **Packaging and Paper-Cardboard:** These fractions, collected through the PaP system and therefore free from contamination, are sent to provincial sorting plants for optimal processing.
- **Glass:** Although collected in containers, the quality and quantity of glass collected have improved indirectly due to the implementation of the PaP system, which has reduced contamination from other waste types.
- **WEEE:** Collected through a dedicated PaP system based on user requests, WEEE undergoes sorting and processing at two plants in Olvera and Villamartín, aiming to maximize preparation for reuse or recycling.
- **Construction and Demolition Waste (RCD):** RCD is processed at a mobile crushing and sorting plant strategically located within the region to minimize transportation distances. The recycled aggregate is utilized for construction and road repair within the Sierra de Grazalema Natural Park, promoting a circular approach to RCD management.
- **Hazardous Household Waste:** Citizens can dispose of hazardous waste, toys, small WEEE, and other minor fractions separately at permanent collection points in municipalities with over 5 000 inhabitants and mobile collection points that service smaller municipalities, ensuring proper management of these materials.

3.6. Citizen Engagement and Awareness

The ECSCA recognizes the crucial role of citizen participation and awareness-raising in achieving its objectives. The project emphasizes:

- **Communication Initiatives:** A comprehensive communication plan, including information campaigns and educational materials, is implemented to inform citizens about the new waste management system and its benefits.
- **Environmental training:** Environmental educators play a vital role in providing guidance, raising awareness, and addressing concerns related to the new system, ensuring that citizens understand the importance of their participation.

- Assistance and Support: The project provides continuous support and assistance to citizens throughout the transition, addressing any challenges and ensuring smooth adaptation to the new model.

The ECSCA's success hinges on fostering a sense of shared responsibility and empowering citizens to actively participate in creating a more sustainable future. By engaging citizens and promoting environmental consciousness, the project aims to drive lasting behavioural change and embed circular economy principles within the community.

3.7. Phased Implementation

The ECSCA was implemented in phases, gradually incorporating municipalities and waste management strategies. This approach was chosen due to the project's scale and the need for careful planning and adaptation to local contexts. Factors considered in defining the implementation phases included:

- Geographic and Urban Characteristics: The diverse landscapes, population densities, and urban layouts of the municipalities required tailored approaches to waste management.
- Existing Waste Management Systems: Integrating the new model with existing infrastructure and practices necessitated a gradual transition.
- Availability of Space: Identifying suitable locations for waste collection, sorting, and treatment facilities was essential for a smooth rollout.
- Community Readiness: Assessing the willingness of residents and local authorities to adopt new waste management practices was crucial for successful implementation.

Door-to-Door (PaP) Collection System:

- Pilot Phase (2019-2020): Zahara de la Sierra and Torre Alháquime were selected for the pilot phase due to their small size, rural setting, and community support. This phase allowed for testing and refining the PaP system before wider implementation.
- Phase 2 (2021-2022): Other small and isolated municipalities were incorporated, coinciding with the commissioning of semi-automatic composting plants. These municipalities were chosen due to their similar characteristics to the pilot locations and the need for localized composting solutions.
- Phase 3 (2022-2024): More populated municipalities are being integrated into the system, with the final phase culminating in the operationalization of the shared composting facility. This phased approach allows for a gradual increase in the volume of waste managed through the PaP system and facilitates adjustments based on lessons learned in earlier phases.

Home Composting Campaign:

- Pilot Phase (2019-2020): Zahara de la Sierra, Torre Alháquime, and El Gastor participated in the initial phase, providing valuable insights into community engagement and the effectiveness of home composting in different contexts.
- Phase 2 (2021-2024): The campaign was expanded to include the remaining municipalities in the Sierra de Cádiz, promoting widespread adoption of home composting practices and reducing reliance on centralized composting facilities.

Rationale for Phased Implementation:

- Testing and Refinement: The pilot phases allowed for the assessment and improvement of the PaP collection system and composting approaches before wider implementation.
- Gradual Capacity Building: The phased approach facilitated the development of necessary infrastructure, including composting facilities and waste collection equipment, in a manageable and sustainable manner.

- Adaptive Management: The project could adapt to local challenges and adjust strategies based on feedback and results from previous phases.
- Community Engagement: The gradual rollout allowed for tailored awareness-raising campaigns and community engagement efforts, ensuring residents were prepared for the transition to the new system.

By progressively incorporating municipalities and waste management strategies, the ECSCA ensures a more effective, efficient, and equitable implementation of the circular economy model. This approach fosters community ownership, promotes continuous improvement, and maximizes the project's impact on waste reduction, resource recovery, and environmental sustainability in the Sierra de Cádiz.

4. RESULTS AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

4.1. Waste Collection and Recycling Rates

The implementation of the PaP system in Sierra de Cádiz has resulted in a significant increase in selective waste collection rates. The project has tripled, and in some cases quadrupled, the selective collection rates compared to the previous container-based system.

The average selective collection rate under the container system was around 10%. After the implementation of PaP, most municipalities now exceed 30%, with some reaching 40%.

The cleanliness of collected fractions has also improved significantly, increasing fivefold. For example, impurities in the packaging fraction have decreased from over 25% to approximately 5%. Although the regulations do not yet mandate minimum selective collection rates for municipal waste until 2035, the project's success demonstrates its potential to meet and exceed future targets.

Fig. 1. Outcomes of the implementation of the PaP collection strategy

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4.2. Composting Outcomes

The ECSCA's composting initiatives have successfully diverted a substantial amount of organic waste from landfills.

The home composting campaign, with 1 429 participating households and 181 establishments (hotels and restaurants), has diverted over 1 500 kg of organic material from landfills daily.

Municipal composting plants in Olvera and Algodonales process 800 kg/day and 400 kg/day of organic waste, respectively, from six municipalities.

The quality of the compost produced is consistently high, meeting Class A or B standards according to Spanish Royal Decree 506/2013 of 28 June 2013 on fertiliser products.

4.3. Socio-Economic Impacts

The ECSCA has had a positive impact on job creation, particularly in the green sector, and on economic development in Sierra de Cádiz.

The project has created 60 jobs, including 46 specialized waste collection operators and compost masters, and the remaining positions filled by environmental educators.

Upon complete implementation, the project is expected to create approximately 100 direct jobs. The project also fosters economic development by establishing a network of waste management companies within the region. This approach contributes to local economic growth and reduces reliance on external service providers.

4.4. Environmental Benefits

The ECSCA contributes to a range of environmental benefits, including:

Reduced Landfill Waste: The project has prevented approximately 12 500 tonnes of municipal waste from ending up in landfills annually.

Decreased Greenhouse Gas Emissions: By composting organic waste locally and minimizing waste transportation, the project reduces greenhouse gas emissions associated with waste management.

Resource Recovery: The ECSCA promotes resource recovery by transforming organic waste into valuable compost and increasing the recycling rates of various waste fractions.

The project's focus on local, decentralized waste management strategies¹³ further minimizes environmental impacts and fosters sustainable practices.

5. CHALLENGES, LESSONS LEARNED, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

5.1. Challenges Encountered

Implementing the ECSCA presented several challenges:

- **Changing Citizen Habits:** Transitioning from a container-based system to PaP required a significant shift in citizen behaviour. Residents needed to adapt to sorting waste fractions and adhering to designated collection days and times¹. Long-standing habits related to waste disposal proved to be a hurdle in the project's initial stages.
- **Logistics in Certain Areas:** Implementing the PaP system proved challenging in areas with scattered populations or multi-storey buildings. The project adopted alternative approaches such as designated collection points and communal PaP systems to address these logistical issues.
- **Continuous Monitoring and Support:** The ECSCA's success hinges on ongoing monitoring of waste collection and composting practices. Providing consistent support and guidance to citizens is essential to maintain high participation rates and address any emerging issues.

5.2. Lessons Learned

The ECSCA offers valuable insights for future circular economy initiatives:

- **Citizen Engagement is Key:** Successfully changing waste management behaviours necessitates active community involvement. The project's emphasis on awareness campaigns, educational initiatives, and ongoing support from environmental educators played a crucial role in gaining public acceptance and participation.
- **Tailored Solutions are Essential:** Designing waste management systems that cater to the specific needs and characteristics of different communities is crucial. Recognizing the logistical constraints in certain areas led to the adoption of alternative PaP models, ensuring wider project applicability.

- **Phased Implementation Enables Adaptive Management:** A phased approach allows for testing, refinement, and gradual capacity building, reducing risks and facilitating project adaptation based on real-world experiences and feedback.

5.3. Replicability and Scalability:

The ECSCA demonstrates significant potential for replication in other regions due to its adaptable framework and successful outcomes:

- **Adaptability to Different Contexts:** The project's modular design, incorporating various PaP and composting models, enables its adaptation to diverse geographic, demographic, and urban settings. The ECSCA has proven effective in both rural and urban environments in the Sierra de Cádiz.
- **Factors Contributing to Success:** Strong community engagement, tailored waste management solutions, and a phased implementation approach are key elements that can be replicated in other locations¹⁵. The project's focus on addressing local needs and empowering citizens to actively participate in waste management fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility.

5.4. Future Directions:

The ECSCA outlines ambitious future goals:

- **Expansion to all Municipalities:** The project aims to cover all municipalities in Sierra de Cádiz, extending the benefits of the circular economy model to the entire region. This expansion will require continued investment in infrastructure, community outreach, and capacity building.
- **Improving Waste Collection and Composting Rates:** The project strives to further enhance selective waste collection and composting rates, optimizing resource recovery and minimizing waste sent to landfills. Achieving these targets will require sustained efforts to engage citizens, refine collection systems, and expand composting infrastructure.
- **Managing Additional Waste Streams:** The ECSCA is exploring the management of additional waste streams, including textiles, furniture, and forestry residues, to further enhance resource circularity and promote economic opportunities within the region¹⁹. Expanding the project's scope will require research, feasibility studies, and investment in appropriate waste processing technologies.

By pursuing these future directions, the ECSCA aims to solidify its position as a leading example of a successful circular economy model in waste management, inspiring similar initiatives and contributing to a more sustainable future.

CONCLUSION

Reiterate the ECSCA's success in revolutionizing municipal waste management in Sierra de Cádiz, underscoring its positive environmental, social, and economic impacts.

Emphasize the project's contribution to advancing the circular economy and achieving sustainability goals.

Conclude by advocating for the replication and scaling of the ECSCA model in other regions, highlighting its potential to transform waste management practices and foster a more sustainable future.

This structure and content outline can be further developed with detailed analysis, data visualization, and relevant academic references to create a comprehensive paper for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank all those who made the ECSCA project possible. Special thanks go to Carmen Moreno, José Domingo García, Alexia Astolfi, Javier Jiménez, María José Cruz Gómez, Carmen Jiménez y María López and the many others whose collaboration has been essential to our success. We also owe a debt of gratitude to the people of the Sierra de Cádiz for their commitment and participation, which have been essential to the project's achievements. Without the collective effort and dedication of all involved, this endeavor would not have been possible.

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Citation: Germán Coca López, Transforming Municipal Waste Management: A Case Study of The Circular Economy Project in Sierra De Cádiz, *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering Research and Development (IJEEERD)*, 2(2), 2024, pp. 1-14.

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